

Influence of weathering impacts on the tightening behaviour of HV and HR bolting assemblies

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ABSTRACT

In preloaded bolted connections, the guarantee of a defined preload level must be given. Bolt manufacturers perform suitability tests according to EN 14399-2 to ensure suitability for preloading e.g. for HV and HR bolting assemblies. While these tests are carried out under controlled conditions in a laboratory, the weathering influences like typical high and low temperatures on construction sites as well as storage and assembling under varying wet/dry conditions are not considered.

EN 1090-2 indicates that uncontrolled exposure conditions can influence the behaviour of the lubrication, which can negatively change the friction conditions and thus also the preload properties. Nevertheless, in daily practice it can be observed that bolting assemblies are assembled under typical high and low temperatures as well as wet conditions, neglecting that the weathering impacts might change the friction conditions of the bolting assemblies and have a severe influence on their tightening behaviour. During tightening on construction site, these influences on the tightening behaviour are not indicatable, but they lead to a high risk of either not achieving the required preload level or leading to an overtightening of the bolting assemblies.

The German national research project (IGF-No. 22379 N) investigates the influence of weathering impacts on the tightening behaviour of HV and HR bolting assemblies under typical working conditions. This contribution intends to present first results regarding the weathering influence, which shows a clear change of the friction coefficients and consequently a change of the tightening behaviour of high strength bolting assemblies.

Keywords: Weathering impacts, bolted connections, suitability test, HV/HR-bolting assemblies

1 INTRODUCTION

In accordance with EN 1993-1-8 (1), bolted connections are categorised into preloaded and non-preloaded bolted connections. The requirements for preloaded bolted connections are stricter than for non-preloaded ones, as it must first be determined whether the selected bolting assemblies are suitable for preloading. In order to verify the approval for preloading and to investigate the tightening behaviour of high-strength bolting assemblies, suitability tests according to EN 14399-2 (2) have to be carried out under laboratory conditions. However, weather influences or deviating temperatures that may occur on the construction site are not considered. Recent experimental studies by Stranghöner et al. at the Institute for Metal and Lightweight Structures (IML) at the University of Duisburg-Essen (UDE) (3) have already shown that different weathering influences can lead to a significant influence on the tightening behaviour of bolting assemblies for preloading. Based on these investigations, the IGF research project (22379 N) covers the effects of weathering for a comprehensive test programme. The presented contribution intends to provide a first insight into the effects of weathering (here in particular at elevated temperatures of +60 °C and humid conditions) on the tightening behaviour of HV and HR bolting assemblies according to EN 14399-4 (4), EN 14399-3 (5) and EN 14399-6 (6).

2 NORMATIV REGULATIONS AND LITERATURE

2.1 European and Northern American normative regulations

The execution of preloaded bolted connections in steel construction is regulated by EN 1090-2 (7) and complemented by the German DASt-Guideline 021 (8) and DASt-Guideline 024 (9). These regulations contain requirements for secure tightening of preloaded bolted connections to defined preload levels. Bolting assemblies for preloading are specified in accordance with EN 14399-1 (10). In order to confirm the suitability of high-strength bolting assemblies for preloading, suitability tests according to EN 14399-2 must be carried out. The purpose of the suitability test is to ensure that the required bolt preload can be achieved reliably and with sufficient reserves without overtightening and failure of the bolting assemblies. Furthermore, the friction in the mating surfaces of bolt nut and washer are checked by the verification of k-values and k-classes. Besides EN 14399-2, EN ISO 16047 (11) also contains tests to determine the tightening properties of bolting assemblies, like friction coefficients, which are primarily influenced by the lubrication.

In accordance with EN 14399-2 and EN ISO 16047 the tightening tests are carried out under laboratory conditions in a temperature range of 10 °C to 35 °C on bolting assemblies in as-delivered conditions. Statements about influences from low and high temperatures (for example -20 °C and +60 °C), which may occur on construction sites, weather influences such as rain as well as frost and improper storage conditions are of course not considered. In EN 1090-2, it is stated that a delay in the tightening process under uncontrolled exposure conditions may alter the performance of the lubrication and that high strength bolting assemblies for preloading shall be used without alteration to the as-delivered lubrication. Weathering impacts can affect the lubrication and thus the tightening behaviour of the bolting assemblies. The German DASt-Guideline 024 also refers to the fact that the lubrication of the bolting assemblies is affected by improper storage and the effects of the weather. At least it is mentioned that the bolting assemblies have to be protected against moisture and dirt and stored under dry and clean conditions.

Neither Part 1 nor Part 2 of VDI-Guideline 2230 (12), (13), which are widely used in mechanical engineering, contains any information on temperature ranges for the design and assembly. Only temperature influences on the bolt preload in the operating state are mentioned.

In North America, high-strength bolting assemblies are regulated by the RCSC specification (14), which references to the ASTM standards for structural joints using high-strength bolting assemblies, such as heavy hex bolts, nuts and washers (15)-(19), which are similar to the high-strength hexagonal bolting assemblies used in steel construction in Europe. The RCSC specification states, that bolting assemblies shall be kept in protected storage and only the needed number of bolting assemblies/components shall be taken from the storage. The storage requirements specify that the as-manufactured conditions of the high strength bolts, nuts and washers are maintained as nearly as possible until they are used at the construction site. It is also mentioned that bolting components or bolting assemblies may be unsuitable for pretensioned installation if they become dirty, rusty, or otherwise have their as-received condition altered. But it may be possible to clean the bolting assemblies and renew the lubrication “*by the fabricator or the erector*”. Furthermore, the standard requires pre-installation verifications up to a daily basis depending on the tightening method to permit the use of the bolting assemblies and tightening method. Bolting assemblies, that do not fulfil the requirements of the individual ASTM standards, are not allowed to be used at the construction site. This type of test is not used in Europe and cannot be implemented due to different legal regulations. For the pre-installation verification and the evaluation of the suitability of the bolting assemblies, there is no defined information about possible environmental impacts given for the test procedure. From a normative point of view, no specific statement is made regarding the tightening behaviour of high strength bolting assemblies influenced by temperatures and different weathering impacts. However, it is not possible to regulate the consideration of weather influences on the tightening behaviour, as this would impair the execution on the construction site. Nevertheless, significant weather-related influences cannot simply be neglected.

2.2 Literature

Tightening tests on high-strength hexagonal and tension control bolts considering various temperatures between -10 °C to +50 °C were carried out by Nah et. al. in Korea (20). The investigation showed that the tightening torque required to achieve the necessary preload decreased with increasing temperature. For the series with a predefined tightening torque, higher bolt preloads were achieved with increasing temperature. Based on these tests, a formula for the estimation of temperature-dependent bolt preload was determined. Kulak and Undershute (21) investigated the influence of humidity and full exposure to the weather for two to four weeks on the tightening behaviour of lubricated high-strength tension control bolts with a high number of different lots respectively manufacturers. The tests on bolting assemblies exposed to humidity resulted only in slightly lower achieved bolt preloads. However, the tension control bolts that were stored outside with full exposure to the weather showed a reduction in the achieved bolt preload.

Stranghöner et al. (3) examined different typical construction site influences like low and high ambient temperatures between -20 °C and +50 °C, moisture and different outside storage conditions with exposure to the weather for up to four weeks on the tightening behaviour of HV- and HR-high-strength bolting assemblies from different manufacturers. Some of the investigated lots of bolting assemblies were influenced significantly by the different weathering impacts and extreme low and high ambient temperature conditions, and others showed no impact by any of these influences.

Dubiel and Grzejda (22) investigated the tightening behaviour for outside stored bolting assemblies that were exposed to the weather for up to four weeks with different configurations (placed open on a concrete base, stored in manufactured cardboard, and more). An influence of the weather on the tightening behaviour could be demonstrated, as the bolting assemblies exposed to the weather showed lower coefficients of friction in the paired contact surfaces of the thread and bearing surface. An investigation carried out by Rutkowski T. (23) showed, that storage on the construction site may lead to corrosion and thus to a deterioration of the tightening behaviour.

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

3.1 Suitability test according to EN 14399-2

To verify the qualification for preloading of high-strength bolting assemblies suitability tests according to EN 14399-2 have been carried out. The main requirements of the suitability test for preloading are shown in Fig. 1. The main requirements have to be fulfilled. The first requirement is

$$F_{bi,max} \geq 0.9 \cdot f_{ub} \cdot A_s \quad (1)$$

where $F_{bi,max}$ is the individual value of the maximum bolt preload achieved during the test,
 f_{ub} is the nominal tensile strength of the bolt and
 A_s is the tensile stress area of the bolt.

The second requirement is

$$\Delta\theta_{2i} \geq \Delta\theta_{2i,min} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\theta_{2i}$ is the individual angle difference and
 $\Delta\theta_{2i,min}$ is the minimum required value of the angle difference of the nut from the first exceeding of the preload $F_{p,C}$ to the angle at which the test is terminated or the preload falls below $F_{p,C}$ again.

The required value of the angle difference depends on the bolting system and the clamp length ratio and is presented in Fig. 1. In addition, k-values are estimated with

$$k_i = \frac{M_i}{F_{p,C} \cdot d} \quad (3)$$

where k_i is the individual value of the k-factor,

M_i is the individual value of the torque applied during the test,

$F_{p,C}$ is the preload level according to EN 1090-2 and DAST-Guideline 024 and

d is the nominal bolt diameter.

The k-values determined for all bolting assemblies must fulfil the requirements of the respective k-classes. The k-class describes the quality of the lubrication of the bolting assemblies, which the manufacturer uses to ensure that the required bolt preload is applied to the bolted connection using a suitable tightening method.

Fig. 1. Suitability test in accordance with DIN EN 14399-2 to verify the suitability for preloading and determining the k-classes

According to EN 1090-2, the tightening method for preloaded bolted connections depends on the k-class. The torque method (for preload level $F_{p,C}$) requires k-class K2, while the modified torque method according to the German DAST-Guideline requires k-class K1. For the combined method the required k-classes are either K1 according to DAST-Guideline 024 or both K1 and K2 according to EN 1090-2. The k-values to be achieved for each k-class are shown in Fig. 1. Although EN 14399-2 does not require evaluating specific tightening methods. When applying the corresponding tightening torque M_A , it should be checked whether the required preload level $F_{p,C}^*$ according to DAST-Guideline 024 can be safely applied to the preloaded connection using the (modified) torque method.

3.2 Modified torque method

Tightening with the modified torque method according to DIN EN 1993-1-8/NA (24), DAST-Guidelines 021 and 024 (021 for diameters larger than M36) is used for the preload level $F_{p,C}^*$ and consists of two main steps. In the frame of the research project the tests were carried out as part of a suitability test. The modified torque method was not used for tightening, but the bolt preload was analysed at the specified tightening torque M_A and compared to the required preload level $F_{p,C}^*$. The requirement is shown as

$$F(M_A) \geq F_{p,C}^* \quad (4)$$

where $F(M_A)$ is the bolt preload at the tightening torque M_A and

$F_{p,C}^*$ is the preload level $F_{p,C}^*$ according to DAST-Guideline 024.

3.3 Test execution and test programme

The suitability tests were carried out on the institute's own tightening torque testing machine in accordance with the requirements of EN 14399-2, see Fig. 2. In addition to test the suitability for

Fig. 2. tightening torque testing machine of the Institute for metal and lightweight structures;
Schematic representation of the tightening torque testing machine measuring concept

preloading and checking the k-values associated with the k-class, the tightening tests are also analysed with the modified torque method. During the tightening process the tightening torque M or T , the angle of rotation θ , the bolt preload F_b and the thread torque T_{th} are measured by the sensors. From the difference between the total torque T and the thread torque T_{th} the bearing surface torque T_b is calculated. Along with the testing parameters of EN 14399-2 the friction coefficients μ_{tot} , μ_{th} and μ_b can be calculated in accordance with EN ISO 16047. However, the results of the friction coefficients will not be discussed further in this contribution. The test programme is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Test programme

Temperature					
Influencing parameter	Diameters	System	k-class	Manufacturers (HS)	Tests per series
+60 °C	M16	HV	K1	3	5
	M16	HR	K2	1	5
	M36	HV	K1	3	5
Moisture					
Influencing parameter	Diameters	System	k-class	Manufacturers (HS)	Tests per series
Simulated rain (5 min)	M12	HV	K1	1	5
	M36	HV	K1	1	5
Immersion (5 seconds)	M12	HV	K1	1	5
	M36	HV	K1	1	5

Two types of weather-related influences are analysed. On the one hand, extremely high ambient temperatures (approx. +60 °C) that can occur on the construction site and, on the other hand, influences from moisture like a short rainfall and water immersion. To compare the results, reference tests were carried out under laboratory conditions in order to determine the respective influence on the preload behaviour.

3.4 Results of suitability tests for preloading under elevated temperatures

To investigate the influence of elevated ambient temperature on the suitability and tightening behaviour of high-strength bolting assemblies, suitability tests according to EN 14399-2 were carried out on different HV and HR bolting assemblies M16 and M36 from different manufacturers (HS) at elevated temperature of +60 °C. The results of the experimental investigations from Stranghöner et al. were also approached for comparison. For the simulation of elevated construction site temperatures, the bolting assemblies were stored at +60 °C in an oven for one hour, see Fig. 3. Within one hour, ASTM E1820 20b (25) ensures that the bolting assemblies used for the tests are entirely heated through. Immediately after bringing one of the bolting assemblies out, the temperature was measured with a contact temperature gauge on the surface of the nut after assembling the bolting assembly into the tightening torque testing machine. The drop in surface temperature was between 2-3 °C.

Fig. 3. Industrial oven for preparing temperature test;
temperature measuring device

Afterwards the tightening test started immediately. The results for the suitability tests for all test series are summarised in Fig. 4. All reference test series fulfilled the requirements $F_{bi,max} \geq 0.9 \cdot f_{ub} \cdot A_s$ and $\Delta\theta_{2i} \geq \Delta\theta_{2i,min}$ as a part of the suitability test according to EN 14399-2. When analysing the bolt preload achieved with the modified torque method according to DAST-Guideline 024 for the reference test series, all bolting assemblies except one of test series HS2-HV-M16-Ref achieved the required preload level $F_{p,C}^*$ after applying the specified tightening torque M_A .

For the tests at elevated temperatures, almost all test series fulfilled the requirements of the maximum bolt preload $F_{bi,max}$ and the minimum required value of the angle difference $\Delta\theta_{2i,min}$, except for test series HS2-HV-M16+60°C. One bolting assembly failed to achieve the maximum required individual bolt preload during tightening.

Two bolting assemblies from each of the test series HS2-HV-M16+60°C, HS4-HR-M16+60°C and HS3-HV-M36+60°C series did not achieve the required preload level $F_{p,C}^*$ with a applied tightening torque M_A . For an exemplary overview, Fig. 5 presents the bolt preload angle of rotation curves and bolt preload-tightening torque curves of the HS3-HV-M36 test series, both for the reference tests at room temperature of approx. 23 °C (black) and for the temperature tests at +60 °C (yellow). A closer look at the reference tests at room temperature (+23 °C) in Fig. 5 and the tests at elevated temperature (+60 °C) shows, that the bolt preload-angle of rotation curves of both conditions have the same curve progressions. Considering the bolt preload-tightening torque curves, an increased maximum torque can be determined during the temperature tests compared to the reference tests. The higher torques results from increased friction, which can be attributed to possible influences from increased temperature on the lubricant applied to the nut in the as-delivered conditions. High tightening torques are not immediately disadvantageous, but should be taken into account more closely, as e.g. the modified torque method depends on the applied torque. For two of the five tested bolting assemblies at elevated temperature, the bolt preload determined at the tightening torque M_A is below the required preload level $F_{p,C}^* = 510$ kN. An overview of the k-values

Fig. 4. Overview of the test results of the suitability test according to EN 14399-2 and evaluation with the modified torque method

Fig. 5. Exemplary illustration comparing the bolt preload angle of rotation curves and bolt preload tightening torque curves between the reference tests at room temperature and the tests at elevated temperature for series HS3-HV-M36

determined as part of the suitability test can be found in Fig. 6. The previously presented HS3-HV-M36 test series shows an increase in the k-values in the temperature tests compared to the reference tests. Despite the increase in the k-value, all the bolting assemblies in this test series fulfil the requirements of k-class K1 with $0.10 \leq k_i \leq 0.16$. Nevertheless, it should be critically noted that despite compliance with the k-values, the bolt preload level $F_{p,C}^*$ was not achieved for two bolting assemblies after evaluation with the modified torque method. Test series HS2-HV-M16+60°C does not fulfil the requirement for k-class K1, as two k-values are above the upper limit of 0.16. In addition, an increase in the coefficient of variation of the k-values from 9 % to 19 % can be recognised. Test series HS4-HR-M16+60°C does not fulfil the requirement of k-class K2 with $0.10 \leq k_m \leq 0.23$ and $v_k = 6 \%$, as the mean k-value k_m is below the limit with a coefficient of variation of $v_k = 8 \%$. However, it is yet not possible to make a generally valid statement on the influences of increased temperatures, as some test series have not shown any significant influences on the tightening behaviour. Further investigations are planned in this regard. Similar findings were also obtained in the studies by Stranghöner et al. (3). Some test series showed no significant influences from the elevated temperature, while others (HS1-HV-M30) fail to meet the requirements for the respective k-class. In addition, the effects of low temperatures (-20 °C) were also analysed. Influences from low temperature on the k-value could also be demonstrated, even if all test series fulfilled the requirements of the respective k-classes.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the experimentally determined k-values between the reference tests at room temperature and the tests at elevated temperatures of approx. +60 °C

3.5 Results of suitability tests for preloading regarding various moisture conditions

In order to investigate the suitability and tightening behaviour of HV bolting assemblies under different moisture conditions, suitability tests according to EN 14399-2 were carried out for the diameters M12 and M36. In the first moisture test group, a rainfall over five minutes on all separate components of the bolting assemblies was simulated. In the second moisture test group, all individual components of the fittings were quickly immersed in water, see Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Box for simulating rainfall; Box with water for immersion

The test series under the influence of rain were tested approx. two minutes after the end of the irrigation. The bolting assemblies of the immersion test series were installed and tested in wet conditions immediately after the bolting assemblies were removed from the water. The results for the suitability tests according to EN 14399-2 for all test series are summarised in Fig. 8. None of the HV bolting assemblies of both moisture test groups for both diameters could fulfil the requirement for the maximum bolt preload with $F_{bi,max} \geq 0.9 \cdot f_{ub} \cdot A_s$. In the M12 reference test series, however, it should be noted that one bolting assembly failed to achieve the required maximum bolt preload as well. Moreover, most bolting assemblies M36 could not achieve the criterion for the required angle difference $\Delta\theta_{2i} \geq \Delta\theta_{2i,min}$.

Two of the bolting assemblies M12 of the immersion tests and one of the rain tests did not fulfil the requirement for the angle of rotation with $\Delta\theta_{2i} \geq \Delta\theta_{2i,min}$. Furthermore, most of the bolting assemblies for both diameters could not fulfil the requirement $0.10 \leq k_i \leq 0.16$ for k-class K1. For the M12 test series, only one of the bolting assemblies sprinkled with water and two of the bolting assemblies immersed in water complied the requirement of the respective k-classes K1. In the case of the M36 bolting assemblies, neither of the bolting assemblies of both test series were able to fulfil the requirements of the k-class K1. In addition, three of the M36 HV bolting assemblies broke when they were disassembled. When analysing the tests with the modified torque method for tightening torque M_A , almost all bolting assemblies did not reach the required preload level $F_{p,C}^*$. Only one of the M12 bolting assemblies in each of the two test series was able to achieve the bolt preload level $F_{p,C}^*$.

Fig. 8. Overview of the test results of the suitability test according to EN 14399-2 and evaluation with the modified torque method for the test series considering moisture conditions

Fig. 9. Comparison of the experimentally determined k-values between the reference tests and tests with moisture

However, it should be emphasised that two of the five tests in the reference series were already unable to fulfil the requirement $F(M_A) \geq F_{p,C}^*$ for evaluation according to the modified torque method. A detailed presentation of the k-values, see Fig. 9, shows that in addition to the non-fulfilment of the requirement for the k-class K1, the coefficient of variation of the k-values also tends to increase. Except for test series HS6-HV-M12-Rain, the coefficient of variation increases between 2 to 5 % compared to the respective reference tests series. However, it should be noted that the coefficient of variation of the k-values in the reference tests is already 8 % for the M12 diameter and 11 % for the M36 diameter. These results are partially consistent with the results of Stranghöner et al. (3). There were some test series that showed no significant influence of moisture on the tightening behaviour. The test configurations were slightly different (like water storage for 3 hours), but a similar influence on the tightening behaviour was nevertheless demonstrated in some of the test series.

4 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

This contribution aimed to provide first insights into the results of construction site's temperatures and weathering influences like moisture on the tightening behaviour of HV and HR bolting assemblies. Based on the presented results, it was possible to demonstrate that weathering influences can lead to negative impacts for the tightening behaviour of bolted connections. Almost all test series at elevated temperatures passed the requirements for the suitability test in accordance with EN 14399-2. However, one test series was unable to fulfil the requirement for k-class K1 and one of the bolting assemblies did not achieve the maximum required bolt preload. The HR bolting assemblies M16 could not fulfil the requirements for k-class K2. Taking the modified torque method into account, two bolting assemblies from each of three test series were unable to achieve the bolt preload level $F_{p,C}^*$ after applying the tightening torque M_A . As this is one of the most common tightening methods in Germany, it must be viewed critically that the required bolt preload level $F_{p,C}^*$ could not be achieved during tightening. Based on the results, it can be shown that the increased temperature has an influence on the preload behaviour and the k-values. These vary depending on the diameters and manufacturers. In the tests with the influence of moisture, significant influences on the tightening behaviour were shown. Irrespective of the influence of moisture (5-minute sprinkling or short immersion) none of the bolting assemblies were able to pass the suitability test, as none of the bolting assemblies could fulfil the requirement for maximum required bolt preload. In addition, a large proportion of the tests did not even achieve the preload level $F_{p,C}^*$.

Further tests are carried out to investigate other weather-related influences such as extremely low temperatures of approx. -20°C on construction sites and improper storage like the exposure of HV and HR bolting assemblies to the weather in delivery boxes and open with no cover on a pallet. The aim of the research project is to quantify the effects of weathering on the tightening behaviour of bolting assemblies and to establish recommendations for action based on the results.

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